

NANOTUBE REINFORCED POLYMER FIBRES

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SUMMARY

A range of different polymer fibres and nanofibres, that contain dispersions of isolated, well-aligned, single wall carbon nanotubes (SWNTs), has been prepared by a number of techniques. The fibres were characterized by Raman spectroscopy which indicated good stress transfer between the SWNTs and polymer fibre matrix during deformation.

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, Raman spectroscopy, Nanofibres, Deformation

INTRODUCTION

It is well established that carbon nanotubes have potentially impressive mechanical properties and it is thought that one of the best ways to realize these properties is to incorporate them in composites [1]. The highest levels of stiffness and strength are obtained for composites when the reinforcing fibres are aligned in one direction. It has also been generally recognized that for any nanocomposite to realize its full potential in terms of mechanical properties the nanophase has to be well-dispersed. Hence, the isolation of reinforcing phases and their alignment are critical stages in the development of these potentially useful materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

In this present study we have prepared PVA nanofibres in which there are low loadings (~ 0.04%) of HiPco SWNTs relative to the PVA [2,3]. This has been undertaken by electrospinning an aqueous PVA solution (8.8% by weight of polymer of molar mass 72,000 gmol⁻¹ in de-ionised water with no surfactant added) containing dispersions of the nanotubes. The electrospinning conditions were as follows: rate of flow = 0.08-2 ml/hour; voltage = 15-25 kV; tip-to-collector distance = 60-120 mm. The electropun nanofibres were collected on aluminum foil and copper TEM grids coated with a holey carbon film. Raman spectra were obtained using a Renishaw 2000 spectrometer fitted with an Olympus optical microscope and a 632 nm HeNe laser as the excitation. Spectra were obtained using a 50× objective lens giving a spot size of the order of 1 µm on the specimen.

The nanofibres were coated with carbon and examined in a FEG SEM (Philips XL30) operated at 5 kV. Figure 1 shows an area of the foil containing a high density of the nanofibres and it can be seen that the individual nanofibres have approximately constant cross-sectional areas and the diameter of the nanofibres ranges from around 1 µm down

to about 20 nm. The nanofibres were also examined in a FEG TEM (Technai F30) operated at 300 kV but it was not possible to resolve the SWNTs in any of the nanofibres, which means that an alternative technique, such as identification using Raman spectroscopy, becomes vital.

Figure 1. SEM micrograph of regions containing a high density of nanofibres

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Raman spectrum of the original HiPco nanotubes is shown in Figure 2a which shows well-defined RBMs, along with the D, G and G' bands for the SWNTs. The Raman spectra from a region containing bundles of nanofibres (e.g. Figure 2a) gives well-defined Raman bands from the SWNTs even though the concentration of nanotubes is very low (only 0.04 % in the nanofibres) because they undergo intense resonance Raman scattering. The spectrum is somewhat weaker than that from the original HiPco material as there are fewer nanotubes in the 1 μm laser spot but the RBM region is very similar in both cases.

A Raman spectrum from an isolated nanofibre (as identified in the optical microscope of the spectrometer) in a region with a low density of nanofibres is also shown in Figure 2a. In this case the spectrum is rather weak and it is shown in more detail in Figure 2b. Closer inspection of the RBM region shows that in this case only a single RBM at 251 cm^{-1} (see inset) can be seen, implying that the nanotube contributing to this spectrum is isolated in the nanofibre. The most remarkable feature of the spectrum is found for the G' band which is split into two well-defined peaks, one at 2596 and the other 2632 cm^{-1} , i.e. equally either side of the G'-band position of 2614 cm^{-1} for the nanofibre bundles in Figure 2a.

The two-peak G'-band behaviour occurs due to a double-resonance process, one in connection with the incident photon and the other with the scattered photon, with each of the two photons resonant with different E_{ii} van Hove singularities in the joint density of states (JDOS). This phenomenon is found only for specific *isolated* SWNTs and not for nanotube bundles.

Figure 2. (a) Raman spectra of the HiPco nanotubes, a nanofibre bundle and an isolated nanofibre. (b) Raman spectrum of the isolated nanofibre showing detail (inset) of the RBM (left) and G' band (right).

It is possible to use polarized Raman spectroscopy to follow the characteristics of the Raman scattering from the SWNTs in the nanofibres and determine firstly the orientation of the SWNTs and secondly if they are isolated from other nanotubes. Figure 3 shows the results of the analysis of the intensity of the G-band scattering from a single nanofibre in a region of low nanofibre density as a function of the angle, ϕ , between the nanofibre axis and direction of incident laser polarization. The results in Figure 3a are for the VV configuration and those in Figure 3b are for the VH configuration. The data have been fitted to the theoretical functions for isolated SWNTs [2] and it can be seen that there is good agreement between the data points and the theoretical curves. This implies that in the specimen used for Figure 3 the SWNTs are both isolated and highly

oriented along the nanofibre axis. The spectrum obtained for low frequency the breathing mode region, inset in Figure 3a, showed a single RBM for this nanofibre at 284 cm^{-1} , consistent with the nanotube being isolated, but in this case the G' band was not split. It should be noted that when there are two resonant nanotubes within the laser spot the dependence of the G-band intensity upon ϕ is more complicated, which gives further confirmation that the nanofibre in Figure 3 contains an isolated resonant nanotube.

Figure 3. G-band intensity for an isolated nanofibre as a function of orientation angle, ϕ , for the two scattering geometries (a) VV (with the RBM inset), (b) VH. (Average of 3 measurements for each data point).

It is possible to estimate the number of SWNTs in the nanofibres from the concentration (0.04 %) of SWNTs. Assuming that they have approximately the same density as the PVA polymer and they are aligned parallel to the nanofibre axis, then for 1 nm diameter SWNTs you should expect to find on average at least one SWNT in the nanofibre as long as it is greater than about 50 nm in diameter. This explains why it was not possible to use TEM to image the SWNTs in the nanofibres. A fibre of 1 μm diameter, on the other hand, such as that used to obtain the data in Figures 2b & 3 would be expected to contain the order of 400 aligned SWNTs. It is interesting to consider, therefore, why the Raman spectra have the signatures of isolated SWNTs.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of the microstructure of a large nanofibre (not to scale). The shaded nanotube is in resonance with the laser excitation whereas the majority of the nanotubes (unshaded) are not. The dashed circle represents the laser spot of the order of 1 μm in diameter.

CONCLUSIONS

Figure 4 gives a schematic representation of the structure of the nanofibres in which there are a number of nanotubes aligned parallel to the fibre axis. Most will not be in resonance with the laser excitation but a small number, such as the one shaded, will be in resonance. Examples will be given of the use of Raman spectroscopy to follow the deformation of these and other nanotube reinforced polymer fibres and further details about them is given in other publications by the authors [2,3].

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References

1. Torstensson, E.T.; Ren, Z.; Chou, T.-W., *Comp. Sci. Tech.*, **2001**, *61*, 1899
2. Kannan, P.; Eichhorn, S.J.; Young, R.J., *Nanotechnology*, **2007**, *18*, 235707
3. Kannan, P.; Young, R.J.; Eichhorn, S.J., *Small*, **2008**, *4*, 930.